

Kinetic and mechanistic studies on the oxidation of DL-aspartic acid with manganese(III) in sulphuric acid medium

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The kinetics of oxidation of DL-aspartic acid by manganese(III) was studied spectrophotometrically at 500 nm in sulphuric acid medium at 40°C. The reaction was observed to be fractional order with respect to substrate and first order with respect to oxidant. Further the rate of reaction found to decrease with increase in ionic strength and [H⁺], while [HSO₄⁻] and [Mn^{II}] were found to have negligible effect. The energy of activation, E_a and the entropy of activation, ΔS^\ddagger computed from thermal studies were found to be 102.23±11.1 KJ mol⁻¹ and 18.45±35.40 JK⁻¹ mol⁻¹ respectively.

Keywords: DL-Aspartic acid, manganese(III), kinetics, oxidation.

Introduction

Aspartic acid is an amino acid useful in maintaining solubility and ionic character of proteins¹. Serum proteins are reportedly essential for maintaining the pH balance of the body. Specifically, aspartic acid is supposed to be involved in the formation of DNA and RNA and in protecting liver¹. It is also supposed to facilitate normal cell function, as well as in increasing endurance and resistance to fatigue by producing immunoglobulins and antibodies. It also reportedly removes highly toxic ammonia from central nervous system¹. Oxidation of aspartic acid was reported with different oxidants like copper(II)¹, hexacyanoferrate², bismuth(V)³, cerium(IV)⁴, quinolinium dichromate⁵ and dihydroxydiperiodatoargentate(III)⁶.

The author has now carried out studies on the oxidation of aspartic acid by manganese(III) in sulphuric acid medium, the results of which are presented in this paper. Manganese(III) is a powerful one electron oxidant in acidic medium. The redox potential of Mn^{III}-Mn^{II} couple is 1.51 volts⁷ in 7.5

mol dm⁻³ sulphuric acid medium and 1.56 volts^{8,9} in 3.0 mol dm⁻³ perchloric acid medium. Manganese(III) is unstable but can be stabilized to some extent by increasing the acidity or by increasing the concentration of Mn^{II} in the Mn^{III} solution. The solution can also be stabilized to significant extent by complexation with sulphate, without much loss in its oxidizing capacity. The stabilization of sulphate ion is attributed to the suppression of disproportion of manganese(III)¹⁷. There are several reports indicating the use of manganese(III) in the oxidation of amino acids and other compounds⁷⁻²⁰.

Sherigara *et al.*¹⁰ studied the oxidation of L-aspartic acid manganese(III) in aqueous sulphuric acid, acetic acid and pyrophosphate media by iodometric method and noticed that the order with respect to [Mn^{III}] changes from two to one as the manganese(III) species changes from aqua ionic to a complex form¹⁰. Further, the authors found first order dependence of rate on [aspartic acid] in all the three media and inverse dependence of rate each on [H⁺] and [manganese(II)].

In view of elucidating the mechanism of DL-aspartic acid with manganese(III) in 1.5 mol dm^{-3} sulphuric acid medium at 40°C , the absorbance of manganese(III) was followed spectrophotometrically at 500 nm. The reaction was found to be fractional order with respect to substrate and first order with respect to oxidant. The rate of reaction found to decrease with increase in ionic strength and $[\text{H}^+]$, while $[\text{HSO}_4^-]$ and $[\text{Mn}^{\text{II}}]$ found to have negligible effect.

Experimental

All chemicals used are AR graded and 99.99% pure (Merck). Aspartic acid of 0.2 mol dm^{-3} strength in 0.2 mol dm^{-3} H_2SO_4 was prepared. A $0.015 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ solution of manganese(III) 5.0 mol dm^{-3} sulphuric acid was prepared by slowly adding 2.3 cm^3 of 0.1 mol dm^{-3} KMnO_4 to an ice cold solution of 50 cm^3 of 0.25 mol dm^{-3} manganese(II) sulphate solution. The resultant manganese (III) was standardized with standard iron(II) solution using ferroin as an indicator.

Kinetic measurements were carried out under the conditions $[\text{H}_2\text{SO}_4] \gg [\text{Asp}] > [\text{Mn}^{\text{III}}]$. Because of considerable disproportionation of manganese(III) even in 2.0 mol dm^{-3} sulphuric acid medium, kinetic runs were carried out in presence of 0.2 mol dm^{-3} manganese(II). The plots of log (absorbance) versus time were found to be linear even beyond two half-lives of completion of the reaction and the rate constants being reproducible within $\pm 4\%$.

Absorption measurements were made with Milton Roy 1201 UV-Visible spectrophotometer using 1 cm path length quartz cells. Temperature of the reaction mixture was kept constant using Siskin Julabo V thermostat.

Results and discussion

The reaction mixture containing 0.03 mol dm^{-3} aspartic acid, 1.5 mol dm^{-3} sulphuric acid, 0.2 mol dm^{-3} Mn^{II} and $3 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ manganese(III) were extracted with diethyl ether after completion of the oxidation. The product was identified as 3-oxo propanoic acid using LC MS. The mass spectrum peak m/z 111.2 amu corresponds to the $(m + 23)$ peak of the product (Fig. 1).

The test for free radicals was carried out by taking aspartic acid and 1.5 mol dm^{-3} H_2SO_4 in thumberg tube and manganese(III) and acrylamide are taken in bent tube. After

evacuating the system, the solutions are mixed by tilting the tube. The reaction mixture was kept aside for 24 h and no turbidity was observed indicating the absence of free radical formation²¹.

The effect of manganese(III) on the rate of oxidation of aspartic acid was observed by studying the reaction varying the initial concentrations of manganese(III) from 2.0 to $4.5 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, keeping all other experimental conditions constant. The plots of log (absorbance) versus time (Fig. 3) were found to be linear beyond 75% completion of the reaction indicating the reaction to be first order with respect to manganese(III) may be seen from the results presented in Table 1.

To observe the dependence of aspartic acid concentration on the rate of reaction aspartic acid concentration was varied from $1.0\text{--}6.0 \times 10^{-2} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ keeping the concentration of all other species constant. The rate of reaction was found to increase with increase in the concentration of aspartic acid. Plots of $1/k$ versus $1/[\text{Asp}]$ at three different temperatures, were found to be straight lines, with positive intercepts on Y-axis, indicating fractional order dependence on the concentration of aspartic acid.

The influence of $[\text{HSO}_4^-]$ on the rate of oxidation of aspartic acid, was studied varying the concentration of $[\text{HSO}_4^-]$, from $1.5\text{--}2.0 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ using sodium bisulphate solution keeping the concentration of all other species constant. It was found that bisulphate ion has practically no effect on the rate of the reaction.

The effect of $[\text{Mn}^{\text{II}}]$ on the rate of the reaction was studied at different concentration of $[\text{Mn}^{\text{II}}]$ varying from $0.2\text{--}0.45 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ using manganese sulphate solution and the influence on the rate of reaction was found to be negligible.

The effect of ionic strength on the pseudo-first order rate constant was studied varying it from $2.0\text{--}4.5 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ using sodium perchlorate solution and as found to have only a marginal effect on the rate of reaction.

Finally the influence of $[\text{H}^+]$ on the rate of the reaction was studied by varying its concentration using perchloric acid, keeping the concentrations of all other reactants constant. It was found that the rate decreased as the concentration of H^+ ion increased.

Fig. 1. Mass spectrum of 3-oxo propanoic acid.

In order to estimate the activation parameters on the rate of reaction was studied at three different temperatures. The energy of activation, E_a and the entropy of activation, ΔS^\ddagger were found to be $102.22 \pm 11.1 \text{ KJ mol}^{-1}$ and $18.45 \pm 35.40 \text{ JK}^{-1} \text{ mol}^{-1}$ respectively.

In sulphuric acid medium, manganese(III) exists in the

form of three different species, as Mn^{3+} , $\text{Mn}(\text{OH})^{2+}$ and MnSO_4^+ . Since bisulphate ion was found not to have any effect on the reaction, MnSO_4^+ may be ruled out as the reactive species. Since increase in H^+ ion concentration caused a decrease in rate, $\text{Mn}(\text{OH})^{2+}$ may be presumed to be the reactive species. Aspartic acid may be regarded as mainly

Fig. 2. Spectrum of manganese(III) in 1.5 mol dm⁻³ sulphuric acid at 30°C.

Fig. 3. Effect of [manganese(III)] on pseudo-first order rate constant, k' .

Table 1. Effect of different reactants on the pseudo-first order rate constant, k' at 40°C

[Mn ^{III}] $\times 10^3$ (mol dm ⁻³)	[Asp] $\times 10^2$ (mol dm ⁻³)	[H ⁺] (mol dm ⁻³)	μ (mol dm ⁻³)	$k' \times 10^4$ (s ⁻¹)
2.0	3.0	1.5	2.0	4.35
2.5	3.0	1.5	2.0	4.40
3.0	3.0	1.5	2.0	4.40
3.5	3.0	1.5	2.0	4.40
4.0	3.0	1.5	2.0	4.35
4.5	3.0	1.5	2.0	4.40
3.0	1.0	1.5	2.0	1.60
3.0	2.0	1.5	2.0	2.86
3.0	3.0	1.5	2.0	4.40
3.0	4.0	1.5	2.0	5.00
3.0	5.0	1.5	2.0	6.34
3.0	6.0	1.5	2.0	7.00
3.0	3.0	1.5	4.0	1.53
3.0	3.0	2.0	4.0	1.28
3.0	3.0	2.5	4.0	1.02
3.0	3.0	3.0	4.0	0.72
3.0	3.0	3.5	4.0	0.61
3.0	3.0	4.0	4.0	0.51
3.0	3.0	1.5	2.0	4.40
3.0	3.0	1.5	2.5	2.81
3.0	3.0	1.5	3.0	2.46
3.0	3.0	1.5	3.5	1.53
3.0	3.0	1.5	4.0	1.28
3.0	3.0	1.5	4.5	1.02

as existing protonated species in 1.5 mol dm⁻³ used in this investigation as may be seen from the protonic equilibria shown in Fig. 4.

Aspartic acid gives three pK values two of them corresponding to α and β carboxylic groups and the third relating

Fig. 4. Protonic equilibria of aspartic acid.

to the amino group. At 1.5 mol dm^{-3} used in this investigation, it may be inferred from $\text{p}K_1$ protonated value at form HAsp.

Mechanism may be therefore be indicated as follows:

From the Michaelis-Menten type of plot between $1/k$ vs $1/[\text{Asp}]$, complex formation between the reactants may be assumed

Hence,

$$\text{Rate} = \frac{-d[\text{Mn}^{\text{III}}]}{dt} = k[\text{C}] = kK[\text{HAsp}][\text{MnOH}^{2+}] \quad (5)$$

But,

$$[\text{Mn}^{\text{III}}]_t = [\text{Mn}^{\text{III}}]_e + [\text{MnOH}^{2+}]_e + [\text{C}]_e \quad (6)$$

$$[\text{Mn}^{\text{III}}]_e = \frac{[\text{MnOH}^{2+}][\text{H}^+]}{K_h} \quad (7)$$

Substituting eq. (7) in (6)

$$[\text{Mn}^{\text{III}}]_t = \frac{[\text{MnOH}^{2+}][\text{H}^+]}{K_h} + \frac{[\text{MnOH}_2^{2+}] + K[\text{HAsp}][\text{MnOH}^{2+}]}{K_h} \quad (8)$$

$$[\text{MnOH}^{2+}] = \frac{K_h[\text{Mn}^{\text{III}}]_t}{[\text{H}^+] + K_h + KK_h[\text{HAsp}]} \quad (8)$$

$$\text{Rate} = \frac{kKK_h[\text{Mn}^{\text{III}}]_t[\text{HAsp}]}{[\text{H}^+] + K_h + KK_h[\text{HAsp}]} \quad (9)$$

This rate equation neatly explains the observed first order with respect to manganese(III), fractional order with respect to [aspartic acid] and decrease in the rate with increasing $[\text{H}^+]$. eq. (9) may be written as:

$$\frac{\text{Rate}}{[\text{Mn}^{\text{III}}]} = k' = \frac{kKK_h[\text{HAsp}]}{[\text{H}^+] + K_h + KK_h[\text{HAsp}]} \quad (10)$$

The above equation inverted to give,

$$\frac{1}{k'} = \frac{[\text{H}^+]}{kKK_h[\text{HAsp}]} + \frac{1}{kK[\text{HAsp}]} + \frac{1}{k} \quad (11)$$

Fig. 5. Plots of $1/k'$ vs $1/[\text{Asp}]$ at three different temperatures.

According to eq. (11) plots of $1/k'$ versus $1/[\text{Asp}]$ should be straight lines with positive intercepts on Y-axis. Such plots have obtained experimentally at three different temperatures supporting the proposed mechanism. These Michaelis-Menten type plots also provide evidence for 1:1 complex between two reactants.

$$\text{For eq. (11) the Intercept} = \frac{1}{k}$$

$$\text{Slope} = \frac{[\text{H}^+]}{kKK_h} + \frac{1}{kK}$$

From the intercepts and slopes of these plots, the rate constants k , for the slow step were computed. Further substituting the values of k and K_h , which is the hydrolysis constant of manganese(III) ($K_h = 0.93$ reported earlier by Wells and Davis²²) in the slope equation, the formation constants K of the complex were computed and the details are presented in Table 2.

Table 2. Values of k and K computed from eq. (11)

[Asp] = 3×10^{-2} mol dm $^{-3}$; [Mn^{III}] = 3×10^{-3} mol dm $^{-3}$; [H⁺] = 1.5 mol dm $^{-3}$;
 μ = 2.0 mol dm $^{-3}$

Temperature (°C)	$k \times 10^{-4}$ s $^{-1}$	K mol dm $^{-3}$
35	3.01	63.62
40	3.94	33.26
45	8.82	31.35

The K values were substituted in the rate law and rate constants k' were calculated. These are compared with experimentally determined values and they were found to be good agreement with each other. The details are presented in Table 3.

Table 3. Comparison of calculated and observed rate constants

[Mn^{III}] = 3×10^{-3} mol dm $^{-3}$; [Mn^{II}] = 0.2 mol dm $^{-3}$; [H⁺] = 1.5 mol dm $^{-3}$;
 μ = 2.0 mol dm $^{-3}$; Temp. = $40 \pm 0.1^\circ\text{C}$

[Asp] $\times 10^2$, (mol dm $^{-3}$)	$k' \times 10^{-4}$ (s $^{-1}$)	
	Obsd.	Calcd.
1.0	1.60	1.61
2.0	2.86	2.89
3.0	4.40	3.94
4.0	5.00	4.80
5.0	6.34	5.50
6.0	7.00	6.18

Conclusion

The oxidation of aspartic acid was carried out with manganese(III) at 40°C in sulphuric acid medium. The reaction was fractional order with respect to substrate and first order with respect to oxidant. Mn(OH)²⁺ is considered to be the reactive species and the proposed mechanism invokes the complexation between Mn(OH)²⁺ and protonated species of substrate. Rate law is derived and activation parameters of slow step are computed.

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